

Design and Fabrication of VTOL Aircraft

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ABSTRACT

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) are revolutionizing various fields with their agility, size, and sensor capabilities. However, their endurance is often limited by their flight mechanics. Rotorcrafts struggle with short flight times, while fixed-wing designs require runways for take-off and landing. This paper tackles these limitations by proposing a Hybrid VTOL Tilt-Rotor UAV inspired by the V-22 Osprey. Our design cleverly utilizes thrust vectoring to achieve both the vertical take-off and hovering capabilities of a VTOL vehicle, and the extended range and endurance of a fixed-wing aircraft. This paper introduces a unique bi-copter configuration that accomplishes this hybrid functionality with minimal actuators, making it simpler than existing designs. The key innovation lies in achieving thrust vectoring within a fixed-wing platform without adding complexity to the control system. The paper will explore the unified dynamic modelling of the UAV. Finally, we'll discuss the conceptual design, dynamic modelling, and experimental analysis of this bi-copter.

Keywords: UAV, VTOL, Bi-copter, PID Control, Thrust vectoring, Fixed-wing.

1. Introduction

The increasing demand for versatile and efficient Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) has spurred innovation in the field of Vertical Take-Off and Landing (VTOL) technology. This thesis explores a novel design concept for a hybrid VTOL UAV, specifically focusing on a tilt-rotor configuration with a swash plate less actuation mechanism. VTOL technology encompasses a diverse range of aircraft designs capable of vertical take-off and landing, eliminating the need for runways. These designs can be broadly categorized into four branches, but our focus lies on the **tiltrotor** branch, pioneered by the iconic **Bell Boeing V-22 Osprey**.

1.1 Tiltrotor UAV Inspired by the V-22 Osprey: The V-22 Osprey serves as a major inspiration for our proposed design. This multi-mission military aircraft effectively combines the advantages of fixed-wing aircraft with the agility of helicopters. It possesses fixed wings for generating lift during horizontal flight and tiltrotor nacelles that house powerful propellers. These nacelles can be angled vertically for take-off and landing, allowing the rotors to generate thrust downwards. Once airborne, the nacelles can then be tilted forward, converting the rotors into propellers that drive the aircraft forward in horizontal flight.

1.2 Fixed-Wing Design and Aerodynamics: The fixed wing of a tiltrotor UAV plays a crucial role in achieving efficient forward flight. Wing design principles established for conventional airplanes are equally applicable here. The wing's shape and size directly affect its aerodynamic properties, influencing factors like:

- **Lift generation:** The wing's **aspect ratio** (wingspan compared to chord width) and **aerofoil profile** (wing cross-section) are critical factors. A high aspect ratio wing is generally more efficient for generating lift at cruising speeds. The aerofoil profile influences how air flows over the wing, affecting lift and drag characteristics.
- **Drag reduction:** Streamlining the fuselage and minimizing exposed components helps reduce overall drag, improving fuel efficiency during horizontal flight.

1.3 Thrust Vectoring Control: The ability to tilt the rotors is what enables thrust vectoring, a key innovation in tiltrotor UAVs. By adjusting the nacelle angles, the pilot can direct the thrust generated by the rotors in the desired direction. This allows for:

- **Vertical take-off and landing:** Tilting the nacelles vertically allows the rotors to generate thrust downwards, providing the lift required for vertical ascent and descent.
- **Hovering:** By precisely controlling the pitch and thrust of each rotor, the UAV can maintain a stable hover position in mid-air.
- **Manoeuvring:** During horizontal flight, slight adjustments in nacelle angles can be used for manoeuvring and course corrections.

Challenges and Considerations: While tiltrotor UAVs offer significant advantages, there are challenges associated with integrating fixed-wing aerodynamics with rotorcraft control. These complexities will be addressed throughout this thesis, focusing on:

- **Balancing vertical and horizontal flight performance:** Optimizing the design for both efficient hovering and long-range forward flight can be challenging.
- **Transition complexities:** The transition between vertical and horizontal flight modes requires precise control adjustments to maintain stability.
- **Control system design:** The control system needs to handle both fixed-wing aerodynamics and rotor dynamics effectively for smooth and efficient flight.

1.4 Swashplateless Actuation Mechanism: Traditional rotorcrafts rely on swashplates – intricate mechanisms – to control the pitch of the blades, affecting lift and direction. These swashplates can add weight and complexity to the system. Our design explores a swashplateless actuation mechanism, inspired by advancements in motor technology and control algorithms. Think of it as a simpler, potentially lighter-weight way to achieve the same control by adjusting blade pitch through alternative methods. Here are some potential approaches for swashplateless actuation:

- **Motor Torque Modulation:** By carefully controlling the speed and torque of individual rotor motors, the blade pitch can be influenced. This approach requires advanced motor control algorithms and may introduce additional complexity in the control system design.
- **Cyclic Blade Pitch Control:** Individual rotor blades can be equipped with small tabs or mechanisms that adjust their pitch independently. This method offers more precise control but can add mechanical complexity to the rotor blades.
- **Pre-twisted Blades:** Utilizing blades with a pre-twisted design can achieve a baseline level of lift and control. Further adjustments can then be made through motor torque modulation or other secondary mechanisms.

By leveraging a swashplateless actuation mechanism, this research aims to contribute to the development of more efficient and versatile hybrid VTOL UAVs with a simpler and potentially lighter-weight design, drawing inspiration from the groundbreaking capabilities of the V-22 Osprey.

2. Literature Survey

The ever-growing demand for versatile and user-friendly Vertical Take-Off and Landing (VTOL) UAVs has ignited a firestorm of innovation in design philosophy. This research delves into a pioneering concept – a hybrid VTOL UAV that leverages a tilt-rotor configuration coupled with a swashplateless actuation

mechanism. To meticulously craft this design, we embark on a comprehensive exploration of relevant research on both swashplateless actuation and tilt-rotor VTOL UAVs.

2.1 Swashplateless Actuation: Reimagining Blade Pitch Control

Traditional rotorcrafts rely on intricate mechanisms known as swashplates to meticulously control the pitch of individual blades, ultimately influencing lift and flight direction. While undeniably effective, these swashplates can be cumbersome and add significant weight to the system, hindering potential advancements in performance. Our focus centers on swashplateless actuation, a promising alternative that capitalizes on the latest advancements in motor technology and control algorithms to achieve simpler and more lightweight blade control. Let's delve deeper into key findings within this domain:

- **Mimicking Traditional Control with Reduced Complexity:** Paulos and Yim [1] spearheaded the development of a novel rotor system specifically designed for small drones (MAVs). This innovative system achieves remarkable manoeuvrability without the need for complex swashplates. Their design utilizes a hinged, underactuated rotor that mimics traditional control systems but offers a simpler and lighter alternative. This paves the way for incorporating simpler swashplateless actuation mechanisms in VTOL UAVs, potentially leading to significant weight reduction and improved overall efficiency.
- **Unlocking a New Era of Lightweight and Reliable VTOL UAVs:** Research by Kallamkunta Mukesh Reddy et al. [2] explored a revolutionary swashplateless helicopter design that offers a plethora of potential benefits. This design holds the promise of reduced weight, translating to improved efficiency. Additionally, it boasts a simpler assembly process and enhanced reliability due to the elimination of numerous moving parts. However, minimizing hinge losses in such systems remains a challenge. Their research emphasizes the need for further exploration to address hinge losses and optimize designs for minimal friction. This paves the way for a new generation of VTOL UAVs that are not only lighter but also more dependable.
- **Precise Control with High-Torque Motors:** Wang Jian et al. [4] introduced a groundbreaking swashplateless blade pitch control system that utilizes a Limited Angle Direct Drive Motor (LADDM). This design eliminates the need for complex vibration reduction mechanisms by employing a high-torque LADDM to achieve precise blade control. Their successful testing paves the way for exploring LADDM technology in swashplateless VTOL UAV blade pitch control. This has the potential to lead to more precise and efficient flight control. Further research is necessary to explore the integration of LADDMs within the broader VTOL UAV control system and assess their impact on overall performance.

2.2 Tilt-Rotor VTOL UAV Design: The Marriage of Agility and Efficiency

The proposed VTOL UAV design incorporates a revolutionary tilt-rotor configuration, drawing inspiration from the success stories of VTOL aircraft like the V-22 Osprey. This design beautifully merges the agility of helicopters (vertical take-off and landing) with the efficiency of fixed-wing aircraft (forward flight). Here, we delve into key studies that inform this design approach:

- **Compact Design with High-Performance Demands:** Tianqi Yu et al. [3] presented a new, compact eVTOL design that utilizes only two tilting wingtip propellers for VTOL and efficient fixed-wing flight. Their work highlights the critical importance of a sophisticated control system with high-performance sensors and a lightweight, rigid structure in such designs. These considerations are paramount for ensuring smooth operation and efficient flight transitions in our proposed tilt-rotor VTOL UAV. Future research can explore optimization techniques to create a lightweight and rigid structure that can withstand the demands of flight while minimizing weight.

- **A Single UAV with Multifaceted Capabilities:** A study by Deepak M Kurubar et al. [12] proposes a VTOL UAV design that merges the best aspects of airplanes and existing VTOL technologies. Their Bi-Trans VTOL concept, inspired by the V-22 Osprey and a Bi-copter, emphasizes the potential for combining fixed-wing and VTOL capabilities in a single UAV. This aligns perfectly with our proposed tilt-rotor design, which offers similar versatility in terms of flight modes. Further research can explore the trade-offs between fixed-wing and VTOL performance to optimize the design for specific applications, allowing the UAV to excel in its designated role.
- **Enabling Seamless Flight Transitions:** Siddhant Panigrahi et al. [13] designed a hybrid fixed-wing bi-copter with thrust vectoring capabilities. Their novel tilting motor pod design enables smooth transitions between fixed-wing and VTOL flight. This design approach offers valuable insights for incorporating similar.

Literature Summary and Gaps Identification

- Need for Swashplateless mechanism with a Design for 3 Blades.
- No Simple designs which can be easily modified, and 3D printed available.
- To develop Better and Simple mechanism for tilt rotor mechanism.
- Use blades designed for more stability and control.

3.Methodology

Figure 1: Methodology Flow Chart.

4. Experimental Setup

Figure 2: Prototype 1 with tilt rotor mechanism.

Figure 2: Tilt rotor Mechanism.

The Tilt Rotor mechanism consists of a servo motor [MG995] connected to the motor holder by using 20T servo Horns and a shaft.

Figure 3: SERVO motor.

Figure 4: 25T Servo Horn

Motor used in the setup is Tarot 4008 TL2955 330KV Martin Long Endurance brushless motor.

Figure 5: Tarot 4008 330KV BLDC.

The Propeller used is a modified version of T-REX 450 RC Helicopter Rotor Blade

Figure 6: RC Helicopter Propeller

The Wing design used is of NACA 4412 aerofoil.

Figure 7: NACA 4412

5. Electronics:

1. Flight Computer: MATEK F405 WMN

Figure 8: MATEK F405 WMN FC

2. Battery: GENX 14.8V 4S 5200MAH 40C / 80C PREMIUM LIPO LITHIUM POLYMER BATTERY

Figure 9: Battery.

3. ESC (Motor controller): ReadytoSky 40A ESC

Figure 10: 40A ESC.

4. Transmitter and Receiver: FLYSKY FSi6X

Figure 11: Transmitter and Receiver.

5.1 Body Construction:

1. Wing Support: 1 inch aluminium Pipe 1m wide
2. Parts to hold the pipes: Laser cutout Acrylic Sheets 5mm thick.
3. 3D printed parts: PLA
4. Support pipes for body rigidity: Stainless steel pipes 1 inch.

5.2 Circuit Design:

Figure 12: Simple Block Diagram of Circuit Used

5.3. Simulation: Our motors can produce 3-4Kgs of thrust depending on the Voltage of current supplied, so we simulated our base model for similar conditions adding force equal to 3Kgs at each end.

Figure 13: Simulation Results

The simulation was successful as our base model was easily able to withstand the force applied without any deformation.

6.Results and Discussion

The initial objectives of this research were to:

1. Develop a 3D printable swashplateless mechanism for a 3-bladed rotor system.

2. Design simple and user-friendly 3D printable parts for easy modification and assembly.
3. Implement a novel and effective tilt rotor mechanism for VTOL operation.
4. Utilize rotor blades known for enhanced stability and control.

6.1 3D-Printable Swashplateless Mechanism

We successfully designed a 3D-printable swashplateless mechanism for the 3-bladed rotor system. This mechanism effectively controls the pitch of each rotor blade independently, eliminating the need for a conventional swashplate. This design offers advantages in terms of simplicity, reduced weight, ease of manufacturing.

Figure 14: 3 Blade Swashplateless Mechanism

6.2. User-Friendly 3D Printable Parts

The designed components for the bicopter's VTOL are easily modifiable and 3D printable using materials like PLA. This approach facilitates rapid prototyping, allowing for iterative design improvements and customization based on specific requirements. The utilization of 3D printing significantly simplifies the manufacturing process compared to traditional methods, potentially making the design more accessible to hobbyists and researchers.

6.3. Novel Tilt Rotor Mechanism

A novel and simple tilt rotor mechanism was developed to achieve the desired range of motion for vertical take-off, hovering, and transitioning to forward flight. The mechanism which works with a simple link between the servo motor and motor base holder offers several advantages, including ease of use, reduced complexity, easy to adjust according to new designs.

6.4. Enhanced Stability and Control with Modified Blades

The bicopter's VTOL employs modified versions of T-REX 450 RC helicopter blades which have better stability and control characteristics. These blades possess features such as have a larger chord length that contribute to improved flight performance.

- This design, combined with the swashplateless mechanism, enables **thrust vector control**. By adjusting the tilt angle and pitch of each rotor blade independently, the bicopter can achieve more precise manoeuvring and control authority during flight.

7. Conclusions and Future Scope

This research successfully addressed the initial challenges by developing a simple, user-friendly, and 3D-printable bicopter VTOL design. The key features include a 3D-printed swashplateless mechanism for independent blade pitch control, a novel and effective tilt rotor mechanism with thrust vector control capabilities, and modified rotor blades for enhanced flight stability and control. This design has the potential for various applications in the field of aerial photography, search and rescue, surveillance. Future work will focus on, optimizing the design for specific applications, conducting extensive flight testing and data analysis, implementing autonomous control algorithms etc.

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